

Condensation of Substituted Acetophenones with Methylene Iodide. Part II. Formation of 1,5-Diketones

D. Chakravarti and Nripendra Kumar Roy

Desoxybenzoin and 2,4-dihydroxy-(phenyl, 5-chlorophenyl, 5-bromophenyl, phenyl-4'-methyl, phenyl-4'-methoxy and phenyl-4'-bromo)benzyl ketones have been condensed with methylene iodide in presence of sodium ethoxide, yielding 1,5-diketones.

Chakravarti and Chakravarti¹ have described the reactions of several resalkano-phenones with methylene iodide in presence of ethanolic sodium ethoxide, leading to the formation of 1,5-diketones, instead of chromanones. The authors have studied in this communication the condensation of substituted phenyl benzyl ketones (I) with methylene iodide with the same condensing agent and found the products as 1,5-diketones (II). In the earlier notes², the products were described as having the isoflavanone structure (III) (by the condensation of one molecule of methylene iodide with one molecule of *o*-hydroxyphenyl benzyl ketone), but the diketonic structure (condensation product of one molecule of methylene iodide with two molecules of *o*-hydroxyphenyl benzyl ketone) is supported by the molecular weight determination, formation of tetra-acetyl, tetramethyl, and 2,4-DNP derivatives, and IR spectra. Wislicenus and Carpenter³ condensed desoxybenzoin (I: R=R'=R''=H) with formaldehyde, yielding (α - γ -diphenyl)- α - γ -bis-benzoylpropane (II: R=R'=R''=H), which was reduced to 1,2-diol (IV). It has been found that desoxybenzoin forms the identical 1,5-diketone, i.e., (α - γ -diphenyl)- α - γ -bis-benzoylpropane (II: R=R'=R''=H), by condensation with methylene iodide in presence of sodium ethoxide and the 1,5-diketone on reduction forms the identical 1,2-diol (IV).

1. *This Journal*, 1963, 40.

2. Chakravarti et al., *Science & Culture*, 1961, 27, 407; 1962, 28, 242.

3. *Annalen*, 1898, 302, 223.

EXPERIMENTAL

($\alpha\gamma$ -Diphenyl)- $\alpha\gamma$ -bis-benzoylpropane (II: R = R' = R'' = H).—A solution of desoxybenzoïn (19.6 g.) in absolute ethanol was added gradually with shaking to a solution of sodium ethoxide (prepared from 2.3 g. Na and 25 ml EtOH). To the resulting solution in cold was added dropwise freshly distilled methylene iodide (20.8 g.) with continuous shaking. After the complete addition of methylene iodide, the reaction mixture was kept at the room temperature for 12 hr. It was warmed on a water bath at 50-60° for about 30 minutes. The cooled solution was then diluted with water and extracted with ether to remove methylene iodide. The insoluble solid substance was filtered and crystallised from ethanol as needles, m.p. 148°, undepressed on admixture with a specimen prepared by the method of Wislicenus and Carpenter³. (Found: C, 85.82; H, 6.00. Calc for C₂₉H₂₄O₂: C, 86.13; H, 5.94%). IR spectra (nujol): $\lambda_{\max}$ 1670, 1580, 1485, 1285, 1255, 1205, 1160, 1060, 1020, 1000, 985, 940, 875, 760, 730, 700 cm⁻¹.

The 2,4-DNP crystallised from benzene as yellow crystals, m.p. 272°. (Found: N, 14.51. C₄₁H₃₂O₈N₆ requires N, 14.66%).

($\alpha\gamma$ -Diphenyl)- $\alpha\gamma$ -bis-benzoylpropane (II: R=R'=R''=H) on reduction with Al-Hg in ethanol-water furnished 1,2-diol(IV), m.p. 139°, undepressed on admixture with a specimen prepared by the method of Wislicenus and Carpenter³.

($\alpha\gamma$ -Diphenyl)- $\alpha\gamma$ -bis-2,4-dihydroxybenzoylpropane (II: R = OH; R' = R'' = H).—2,4-Dihydroxyphenyl benzyl ketone⁴ (I: R = OH; R' = R'' = H) (11.4 g.) was condensed with methylene iodide (14 g.) in presence of sodium ethoxide. The reaction product, isolated in the usual way, crystallised from glacial acetic acid as colorless rods, m.p. 192° [Found: C, 74.35; H, 5.12; M.W. (Rast), 474. C₂₉H₂₄O₆ requires C, 74.61; H, 5.12%; M.W., 468]. It develops a violet colour with ethanolic ferric chloride solution.

UV spectra: $\lambda_{\text{EtOH}}^{\max}$ 260 m μ , 337 m μ . IR spectra (nujol): λ_{max} 3400, 3200, 1615, 1490, 1250, 1225, 1200, 1190, 1160, 1100, 1060, 1025, 995, 940, 920, 875, 845, 725, 690 cm⁻¹.

The mass spectrograph* of the substance provided a very intensive peak at mass 137 and other peaks at 151 and 228.

4. Bhungara *et al.*, *Proc. Ind. Acad. Sci.*, 1947, 25A, 322.

*The authors are indebted to Dr. W. Simon [Laboratorium für Organische Chemie, Eidg. Technische Hochschule, Zürich] for mass spectrography.

The *tetramethyl ether* crystallised from ethanol as prismatic rods, m.p. 136-37°. (Found: C, 75.30; H, 6.32. $C_{33}H_{32}O_6$ requires C, 75.57; H, 6.10%.)

($\alpha\gamma$ -Diphenyl)- $\alpha\gamma$ -bis-2,4-dihydroxy-5-chlorobenzoylpropane (II: R=OH; R'=Cl; R''=H) was prepared in the above way by condensing 2,4-dihydroxy-5-chlorophenyl benzyl ketone⁵ (I: R=OH; R'=Cl; R''=H) (2M) with methylene iodide (1M) in presence of sodium ethoxide. The diketone crystallised from glacial acetic acid as silky needles, m.p. 229-30°. [Found: C, 64.50; H, 4.12; M.W. (Rast), 536. $C_{29}H_{22}O_6Cl_2$ requires C, 64.61; H, 4.09%; M.W., 537]. IR spectra (nujol): λ_{max} 3350, 1625, 1585, 1400, 1285, 1220, 1125, 1050, 1000, 930, 880, 845, 760, 750, 700 cm^{-1} . It shows a violet colour with ethanolic ferric chloride solution.

The *tetra-acetyl* derivative crystallised from dilute ethanol as rectangular plates, m.p. 125°. (Found: C, 62.63; H, 4.12. $C_{37}H_{30}O_{10}Cl_2$ requires C, 62.97; H, 4.25%.)

($\alpha\gamma$ -Diphenyl)- $\alpha\gamma$ -bis-2,4-dihydroxy-5-bromobenzoylpropane (II: R=OH; R'=Br; R''=H) was prepared by condensing 2,4-dihydroxy-5-bromophenyl benzyl ketone⁵ (I: R=OH; R'=Br; R''=H) (2M) with methylene iodide (1M) in presence of sodium ethoxide. It was crystallised from glacial acetic acid in silky needles, m.p. 225°. (Found: C, 55.56; H, 3.40. $C_{29}H_{22}O_6Br_2$ requires C, 55.59; H, 3.51%). It develops a violet colour with ethanolic ferric chloride solution.

IR spectra (nujol): λ_{max} 3350, 1625, 1585, 1400, 1290, 1225, 1125, 1050, 1000, 920, 875, 845, 760, 740, 690 cm^{-1} .

The *tetra-acetyl* derivative crystallised from dilute ethanol as rectangular plates, m.p. 140°. (Found: C, 55.80; H, 3.58. $C_{37}H_{30}O_{10}Br_2$ requires C, 55.91; H, 3.77%.)

($\alpha\gamma$ -Di-p-tolyl)- $\alpha\gamma$ -bis-2,4-dihydroxybenzoylpropane (II: R=OH; R'=H; R''=Me). —2,4-Dihydroxyphenyl-4'-methylbenzyl ketone⁶ (I: R=OH; R'=H; R''=Me) (2M) was condensed with methylene iodide (1M) in presence of sodium ethoxide. The compound was isolated as in the previous cases. It was crystallised from glacial acetic acid as rods, m.p. 218°. (Found: C, 74.82; H, 5.38. $C_{31}H_{28}O_6$ requires C, 75.00; H, 5.64%). It shows a violet colour with ethanolic ferric chloride solution.

IR spectra (nujol): λ_{max} 3350, 1625, 1580, 1485, 1390, 1290, 1220, 1160, 1100, 1050, 910, 825, 775 cm^{-1} .

The *tetra-acetyl* derivative crystallised from dilute ethanol as rectangular plates, m.p. 132°. (Found: C, 70.29; H, 5.48. $C_{39}H_{36}O_{10}$ requires C, 70.48; H, 5.42%.)

($\alpha\gamma$ -Di-p-anisyl)- $\alpha\gamma$ -bis-2,4-dihydroxybenzoylpropane (II: R=OH; R'=H; R''=OMe) was prepared by condensing 2,4-dihydroxyphenyl-4'-methoxybenzyl ketone⁷ (I: R=OH; R'=H; R''=OMe) with methylene iodide (1M) in presence of sodium ethoxide. The compound, isolated in the usual way, was crystallised from glacial acetic acid as

5. Roy and Chakravarti, this *Journal*, 1963, 40, 601.

6. Chapman and Stephen, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1923, 123, 408.

7. Baker and Eastwood, *ibid.*, 1929, 2902.

prismatic rods, m.p. 195°. (Found: C, 70.26; H, 5.10. $C_{21}H_{28}O_8$ requires C, 70.45; H, 5.30%). It develops a violet colour with ethanolic ferric chloride solution.

The *tetra-acetyl* derivative was crystallised from dilute ethanol as rectangular plates, m.p. 130°. (Found: C, 67.01; H, 4.98. $C_{39}H_{36}O_{12}$ requires C, 67.24; H, 5.17%).

2,4-Dihydroxyphenyl-4'-bromobenzyl Ketone (I: R = OH; R' = H; R'' = Br).—*p*-Bromobenzyl cyanide (12 g.) and resorcinol (6.6 g.) were dissolved in dry ether (50 ml). Powdered zinc chloride (4 g.) was added and the solution was saturated with dry HCl at 0° for about 6 hr. After keeping overnight the reaction mixture was hydrolysed by heating with water (50 ml) for 1 hr. The ketone was then extracted with chloroform and the extract was treated NaOH solution (dil.). Acidification of the above solution provided a solid, which crystallised from dilute ethanol in needles, m.p. 100-101°. (Found: C, 54.53; H, 3.26. $C_{14}H_{11}O_3Br$ requires C, 54.72; H, 3.58%). It develops a deep violet colour with ethanolic ferric chloride solution.

[α -*Di*-(*p*-bromophenyl)]- α -*Di*-2,4-dihydroxybenzylpropane (II: R = OH; R' = H; R'' = Br).—2,4-Dihydroxyphenyl-4'-bromobenzyl ketone (2*M*) was condensed with methylene iodide (1*M*) in presence of sodium ethoxide in the usual way. The compound, isolated in the above way, was crystallised from glacial acetic acid in prismatic rods, m.p. 265°. (Found: C, 55.48; H, 3.21. $C_{29}H_{22}O_6Br_2$ requires C, 55.59; H, 3.51%). It develops a violet colour with ethanolic ferric chloride solution.

FIG. 1

1. Compound II (R = OH; R' = H; R'' = Me) (.....)
 2. Compound II (R = OH; R' = Br; R'' = H) (————)

The authors offer their thanks to Shri Nirendra Nath Chakravarti for his help and to Mr. B. B. Bhattacharyya, Jadavpur University, for the microanalyses of the samples.